

SYNTHESIS OF CYANINE DYES BY THE CONDENSATION OF *p*-DIETHYLAMINO-
BENZALDEHYDE WITH APPROPRIATE HETEROCYCLIC
COMPOUNDS. PART II.

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In view of the fact that the cyanine dyes of the thiazole series are commercially valuable sensitizers, five new dyestuffs of this group have been synthesised by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with the methiodides of 2 : 4-dimethylthiazole, 2-methyl-4-phenylthiazole, 2-methylbenzothiazole, 2-methyl- α -naphthathiazole and 2-methyl- β -naphthathiazole. The chemical, dyeing, optical and photographic properties of these compounds have been examined. A comparison has also been made with the corresponding dimethylamino derivatives prepared by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with these heterocyclic ammonium compounds. The preparation of some of the "intermediates" has also been described.

In view of the fact that in modern photographic plate manufacture cyanine dyes of the thiazole series (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2262; König and Treichel, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1921, 102, 63; Mills and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2724; Smith, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 2288; König, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 2065; Hamer, *I. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2598; Fisher and Hamer, *ibid.*, 1930, 2502; Ogata, *Proc. Imp. Acad. Tokyo*, 1933, 9, 602; Brooker and White, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2480; Kiprianov, Sitnik and Sitsch, *J. Gen. Chem. Russia*, 1936, 6, 42, 576; Beilenson and Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1225; Kiprianov and Sitsch, *Trans. Inst. Chim. Charkov*, 1936, 2, 15) are being increasingly used, it was of interest to synthesise and examine the properties of a new class of sensitising dyes, prepared by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (*cf.* B.P. 449527) with quaternised thiazole bases containing a reactive methyl group, represented by the general formula (D). It was also intended to study the change in photographic properties of these dyes with increase in the size of the thiazole nucleus, and for this reason, two simple thiazoles, one benzothiazole, and two naphthathiazole derivatives have been chosen for these condensations; the quaternary compound being prepared in each case by the addition of methyl iodide. Thus structurally the dyes differed from one another only in the nature of their thiazole nuclei.

The dyestuffs have been prepared by the interaction of the methiodides of 2-methyl-4-phenylthiazole, 2-methylbenzothiazole, 2-methyl- α -naphthathiazole and 2-methyl- β -naphthathiazole with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde in absolute alcoholic solution, catalysed by small quantities of piperidine. In the case of 2 : 4-dimethylthiazole-methiodide, the condensation is effected in acetic anhydride solution, and no catalyst is used. It has been noticed that the methiodides of simple thiazoles undergo dye-condensation of this kind less readily than the methiodides of condensed thiazole systems.

Some of the properties of these dyestuffs are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour, shape and "Form"	M.P.	Colour in cold conc. H_2SO_4 .	Reflex.	P L E O C H R O I S M		REMARKS	Relative intensity of colour in solution	Relative resistance to decolorisation	EXTRA SENSITIZATION RANGE. MAXIMUM.
					Light in one position of through 90° Polariser	Colour after rotation				
V	Dark steel blue, thin elongated needle clusters, (Hypidomorphic)	157-158°	Pink	Weak, Bluish green	Brownish red	Pink	Some of the crystals shine like mica	1	1	5200-6000 Å 5450 Å
W	Beautiful shining, greenish blue, stout needles (Idiomorphic)	211-212°	Pinkish brown	Strong, Greenish blue	Amethyst	Deep reddish violet	Some surfaces look like plate glass	1.53	1.4	5150-6450 Å 5600 Å
X	Bronze, felted needles (Allotrimorphic) volume from 140°	224° (begins to shrink in 140°)	Brownish-pink	Strong, Old Gold	Nil	Nil	Looks like glass thread	1	8.5	5200-6350 Å 5700 Å
Y	Dirty green, spheroidal granules	243-244°	Flourescent, dirty green	Very weak, Grass green	Yellowish grey	Brassy yellow	Bigger particles exhibit beautiful greenish fluorescence	1.15	2.7	5400-5950 Å Not definite
Z	Sage green granular crystals	173-174°	Flourescent, yellowish green	Strong, Bottle green	Light yellow	Opaque	Some of the crystals shine like yellow diamond	1.07	2.2	5450-6500 Å 5750 Å

Note :—(V), (W), (X), (Y) and (Z), represent respectively the methiodides of 2-p-dichthylaminostryl—, —4-methyl-thiazole; —4-phenyl-thiazole; —Benzo-thiazole; —6-Naphthathiazole and —8-Naphthathiazole.

All the five compounds are insoluble in cold but very slightly soluble in boiling water. They are freely soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *iso*amyl alcohol, chloroform and acetic acid, and insoluble in ether and benzene, except (V) which is moderately soluble in the latter solvent.

Dilute solutions are all coloured, the two substituted simple thiazole derivatives (V) and (W) being reddish yellow, the reddish tinge increasing with increase in molecular weight; and the three condensed thiazole derivatives (X), (Y) and (Z), are magenta coloured, the colour deepening with increasing molecular weight. The relative intensities of dilute solutions (1 : 100000) of these two sets of compounds in rectified spirit as determined by means of a Duboseq Colorimeter (Snell, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis," 1936, p. 43, Chapman and Hall Ltd.) are given in Table I.

It will be noticed that the introduction of a phenyl group in 4-position in the simple thiazole derivative in place of methyl increases the intensity of colour by about 50%. Among the condensed thiazole derivatives, the α -naphthathiazole compound forms relatively the most intensely coloured solution.

As compared with the corresponding symmetrical carbocyanines (Mills, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 455; Hamer, *ibid.*, 1929, 2598; Fisher and Hamer, *ibid.*, 1930, 2502) these unsymmetrical cyanines are less deeply coloured. This is due to the lower degeneracy of these unsymmetrical cyanines, brought about by the presence of the single benzene ring in the chromophoric chain which is known to inhibit resonance along that chain.

TABLE II

Methiodide of	Corresponding <i>p</i> -diethylamino compound	Appearance of solid	M.p.	Colour in dilute solution.	Reflex.	Sensitisation Extends Maximum to		Reference
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostyryl-4-methylthiazole-	(V)	Red needles	269°	Deep orange	Blue	5950* Å	5500* Å	Smith, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 123, 2291
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostyryl-4-phenylthiazole-	(W)	Ruby red crystals	243°	Deep orange	Bluish green	6200	5500	Mills and Smith, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1922, 121, 2735
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostyryl-benzothiazole-	(X)	Steel blue needles	250°	Purple	<i>nil</i>	6700	5700	Smith, <i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1923, 123, 2292
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostyryl- α -naphthathiazole-	(Y)	Prismatic crystals	232°	Magenta	Green	6800	5900	<i>idem.</i> , page 2294
2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostyryl- β -naphthathiazole-	(Z)	Lustrous blue needles	256°	Purple	<i>nil</i>	6700	6100	Do.

The symmetrical dyes, on the other hand, on account of the identity of the two heterocyclic nuclei, possess completely degenerate resonance structures, and are therefore more deeply coloured (Brooker and Sprague, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3203; also see Brooker *et al.*, *ibid.*, p. 3192; Brooker and Sprague, *ibid.*, p. 3214; Brooker, Keyes and Williams, *ibid.*, 1942, 64, 199; Brooker, *Rev. Modern Physics*, 1942, 14, 275).

The unsymmetrical and symmetrical cyanines resonate according to the schemes $I(a) \longleftrightarrow I(b)$ and $II(c) \longleftrightarrow II(d)$ respectively.

In a resonating system, the benzenoid configuration is known to be more stable than the quinonoid, and hence the actual state of the compound (I) will tend towards $I(a)$. The compound will therefore lose, in corresponding measure, its nature as a resonance hybrid, and its colour will be lighter in consequence. There is no such degeneracy-inhibiting factor in (II), the two states have nearly the same energy and therefore nearly the same stability, which means higher resonance, higher degeneracy, and deeper colour.

A noteworthy observation, the explanation of which is obscure at present, is that the acetic acid solutions of these dyestuffs deepen in colour on warming. When the solutions are cooled the intensity diminishes and the original colour is slowly regained. The effect is more pronounced in aqueous-acetic acid solutions.

Like other cyanine dyes the colour of the solutions of these compounds is reversibly discharged by the addition of mineral acids. In Table I is given the "relative resistance" of these newly synthesised dyestuffs to decolorisation by $N/100$ hydrochloric acid. The exceptional resistance of the benzothiazole derivative (X) is particularly noticeable. The difference between the α - and β -naphthathiazole compounds having the same molecular weight, is remarkable.

The discharge of colour by the addition of mineral acids (*cf.* Brooker, Sprague, Smyth and Lewis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1116) is probably due to the destruction of the conjugated system, responsible for the colour of the dyestuff, as suggested in (E)

Silk, wool and cotton have been dyed with these compounds in the usual way (Whittaker and Wilcock, "Dyeing with Coal-tar Dyestuffs", 1939, Bailliere Tindall & Cox, London)

FIG. 1(a)

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FIG. 1(b).

and the shades obtained are recorded in Table III. None of the shades is fast either to sunlight or to soaping. When exposed to sunlight, the colour of (Y) is discharged most rapidly and that of (V) most slowly.

TABLE III

Compound	Colour produced on		
	Silk	Wool	Cotton
(V)	Pinkish orange	Pinkish orange	Pink
(W)	Crimson	Light blood red	Bluish crimson
(X)	Violet red	Reddish violet	Purple
(Y)	Mauve	Violet	Mauve
(Z)	Mauve	Violet	Mauve

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions (1 : 100000) of these compounds (*cf.* Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1940, 17, 348) is given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Wallace Filter No.	Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam				
	(V)	(W)	(X)	(Y)	(Z)
1	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed
2	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Weak brownish red	Very weak red
3	Sulphur yellow	Weak yellow	Brownish yellow	Pinkish red	Reddish yellow
4	Light absorbed	Light absorbed	Weak brown	Flaming red	Orange red
5	Lemon yellow	Lemon yellow	Yellowish brown	Yellowish red	Yellowish red
6	Deep lemon yellow	Brownish yellow	Dirty yellow	Yellowish red	Brownish red
7	Greenish brown	Greenish yellow	Greenish yellow	Orange red	Brownish red
8	Brownish yellow	Brownish yellow	Brownish orange	Orange red	Flaming red
9	Bluish white	Orange yellow	Carrot yellow	Dull bluish red	Bluish red
10	Brownish yellow	Bright yellow	Brownish yellow	Orange red	Dirty yellow

Photographs of absorption and sensitisation spectra of all the five compounds, determined by means of a Wedge spectrograph, are shown in Fig. 1. For the sake of comparison, in each case, the absorption spectrum is given below the sensitisation spectrum. Among the compounds examined, the β -naphthathiazole derivative (Z) is the most powerful sensitiser, extending the sensitisation up to λ 6500. The extra-sensitisation, however, although extensive, is not very intense. The α -naphthathiazole compound (Y), on the other hand, is the poorest sensitiser of the whole lot. (W), the 4-phenylthiazole compound is a valuable "green" sensitiser, suitable for the manufacture of orthochromatic plates. Its extra-sensitisation is not only intense, but is also free from the common defect of a "gap" in the blue green region of the spectrum. Except in the case of the α -naphthathiazole compound (Y), increase in molecular weight of the dyestuff, extends the band of extra-sensitisation farther towards the red end of the spectrum. The salient features of the sensitisation spectra of these compounds are summarised in Table I.

Like other styryl compounds (Bloch and Hamer, *Phot. J.*, 1930, 54, 374) the absorption spectra are all single banded, reflecting the essential similarity in the structure of these compounds.

From the point of view of similarity in properties, the five compounds investigated fall into two groups. The first comprises the two simple thiazole derivatives (V) and (W), which have nearly the same colour, similar absorption and similar sensitisation. The second group consists of the three condensed thiazole derivatives (X), (Y) and (Z). Notwithstanding their identical molecular weights and very similar structure, the great difference in the sensitising powers of α - and β -naphthathiazole compounds (Y) and

(Z) are noteworthy. In their yields and solubility in methyl alcohol too, they markedly differ. The β -compound (Z) is more freely soluble and also gives a higher yield than the α -compound. It is interesting to compare these results with the observations of Hamer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2601, 2606) in regard to the corresponding 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyryl- α - and - β -naphththiazole ethiodides. She has also found the β -compound to be more soluble in methyl alcohol than the α -compound. In the matter of yields, however, reverse is the case, it is the α -compound which gives the higher yield.

In order to compare the properties of these new dyestuffs with the corresponding dimethylamino compounds (prepared by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with the same heterocyclic ammonium bases as have been used in the synthesis of the compounds described in this paper) the properties of the latter have been collected from relevant publications and summarised in Table II. It will be seen that with the exception of the α -naphththiazole derivative, the dimethylamino compound in every case, has a higher m.p. than the corresponding diethylamino compound, notwithstanding the increased molecular weight of the latter. In the matter of photographic sensitisation the two simple thiazole derivatives of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (V) and (W) are slightly more powerful than the corresponding dimethylamino compounds. The three condensed thiazole derivatives (X), (Y) and (Z), however, are much less powerful than the corresponding dimethylamino compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

2 : 4-Dimethylthiazole-methiodide.—2 : 4-Dimethylthiazole was prepared according to the method of Hantsch (*Annalen*, 1889, 250, 270) and obtained in a yield of 58.4% (Hantsch does not record the yield of his compound). It was quaternised by Hamer's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2509) and was obtained as pink needles even after five recrystallisations with m.p. 268° (Hamer's crystals were colourless and had m.p. 260°). (Found : I, 50.05. $C_6H_{10}NIS$ requires I, 49.8 per cent).

2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-4-methylthiazole-methiodide (V).—*p*-Diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.72 g.) and 2 : 4-dimethylthiazole-methiodide (1.02 g.) were dissolved in acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) and the solution refluxed for 4 hours. The reaction started even in the cold, as was indicated by the change in the colour of the solution. The red solution was concentrated to about half its volume and then left for 4 days. The separated crystals (0.4 g.) were recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, yield 0.2 g. (12.1%). (Found : N, 6.87 ; I, 30.50. $C_{17}H_{23}N_2IS$ requires N, 6.76 ; I, 30.67 per cent).

4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole-methiodide.—4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole was prepared from acetamide and phenacyl bromide as described by Hantsch (*loc. cit.*), and was converted into its methiodide by the method of Mills and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2735). It was obtained in the form of slightly reddish crystals, the colour of which deepened on keeping, melting at 200° (Mills and Smith give m.p. 202°). The yield of the base was 80% and that of the methiodide 50% (neither Hantsch nor Mills and Smith record the yields of their compounds).

2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-4-phenylthiazole-methiodide (W).—*p*-Diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.54 g.), 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole-methiodide (0.96 g.), absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and piperidine (5 drops) were heated together for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was

placed in a frigidaire overnight and the separated crystals (1.0 g.) recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 0.9 g. (62.5%). (Found : N, 6.02 ; I, 26.31. $C_{22}H_{22}N_2IS$ requires N, 5.88 ; I, 26.68 per cent).

2-Methylbenzothiazole-methiodide.—This compound has been mentioned by Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2292) but the details of the preparation have not been given. We obtained it by heating 2-methylbenzothiazole (1 mol.), prepared by oxidising thioacetamide with potassium ferricyanide (Jacobson, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1072 ; Clark, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2313 ; Guha and Ghosh, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1929, 12, 34) and methyl iodide (1.5 mol.) in a sealed tube for 24 hours. The resulting white crystalline mass was recrystallised from rectified spirit. The methiodide consists of colourless plates, m.p. 219°. (Found : I, 43.92. $C_9H_{10}NIS$ requires I, 43.64 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-benzothiazole-methiodide (X).—On heating a solution of 2-methyl-benzothiazole-methiodide (0.58 g.) and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.36 g.) in absolute alcohol (8 c.c.) with piperidine (0.1 c.c.), a red colour developed immediately. After boiling for one hour and cooling, crystals of the dyestuff were deposited (0.57 g.). These were recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 0.48 g. (53.9%). (Found : N, 6.56 ; I, 28.02. $C_{23}H_{22}N_2IS$ requires N, 6.22 ; I, 28.22 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl- α -naphthathiazole-methiodide (Y).—2-Methyl- α -naphthathiazole-methiodide (Jacobson, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2627 ; Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2602) (2.05 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.08 g.), absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and piperidine (6 drops) were boiled together for a couple of hours. The dyestuff began to separate from the boiling solution. The mixture was allowed to cool, the crystals filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield, 1.25 g. (41.6%). (Found : N, 5.69 ; I, 25.29. $C_{24}H_{22}N_2IS$ requires N, 5.60 ; I, 25.40 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl- β -naphthathiazole-methiodide.—On refluxing 2-methyl- β -naphthathiazole-methiodide (Jacobson, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1897 ; Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2601) (0.68 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.36 g.), absolute alcohol (7.5 c.c.) and piperidine (0.3 c.c.), for 3 hours the dye was deposited. The ether-washed crystals were recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield, 0.6 g. (60.0%). (Found : N, 5.72 ; I, 25.37. $C_{24}H_{22}N_2IS$ requires N, 5.60 ; I, 25.40 per cent).

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